

**FUNCTIONAL AND SEMANTIC ASPECTS OF THE NOUN IN THE
UZBEK AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES**

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Abstract. This article examines the functional and semantic features of the noun in the Uzbek language. It analyzes its grammatical categories, syntactic functions, and semantic classification. Special attention is given to the interaction between form and meaning, as well as the role of the noun in shaping the semantic structure of the utterance.

Keywords: noun, semantics, function, grammatical category, Uzbek language, syntax, word formation.

Introduction

The noun is one of the central parts of speech in any language, including Uzbek. It performs essential syntactic functions and serves as the main carrier of lexical, grammatical, and semantic information. From a functional-semantic perspective, the noun is studied not only in terms of its grammatical forms but also its meaning

and communicative role.

In both Russian and Uzbek, nouns are autonomous words denoting names of objects or phenomena. Both languages share the grammatical categories of case and number, yet they differ in how these categories are expressed. For example, in Uzbek, the plural form is formed by simply adding the suffix *-lar*, whereas in Russian, the plural is formed through a variety of affixes depending on the word's stem type, hardness, or softness.

When it comes to number, some Russian nouns (such as *молоко, сметана, хлопок, мясо, любовь, храбрость, молодость*) have no plural form, while others (*часы, брюки, ворота, ножницы, сани, каникулы, шахматы, Сочи*) exist only in the plural. Similarly, in Uzbek, certain abstract nouns such as *suv* (вода - water), *don* (зерно - grain), *halq* (люди - people), *roda* (стадо - herd) generally appear only in the singular, but they may acquire plural meaning in specific contexts by adding the plural suffix *-lar*.

In Russian, possessive meanings are expressed by combining nouns with possessive pronouns (*мой карандаш, моя книга, моё яблоко, мои студенты*). Meanwhile, Uzbek relies primarily on possessive suffixes for this function.

The grammatical category of gender, inherent to most Indo-European languages, is entirely absent in Turkic languages, including Uzbek. Therefore, distinctions of biological sex are expressed only in lexical or syntactic ways when referring to humans and animals.

Means of Expressing Gender in Uzbek Nouns

1. Lexical Means.

In many cases, gender meaning is embedded in the lexical semantics of the word itself (cf. Russian *отец – мать, петух – курица*). Similar distinctions appear in Uzbek:

- **Terms of kinship and human relationships:** *ota* (отец - father), *ona* (мать - mother), *o'g'il* (сын - son), *qiz* (дочь - daughter), *amaqi* (дядя (по отцу) - uncle,

paternal), amma (тетя (по отцу) - aunt, paternal), toga (дядя (по матери) - uncle, maternal), xola (тетя (по матери) - aunt, maternal), aka (старший брат - elder brother), opa (старшая сестра - elder sister), uka (младший брат - younger brother), singil (младшая сестра - younger sister), er (самец - husband, мужчина - man), ayol, xotin (женщина - woman), urg'ochi (самка - female, animal).

- **Names of domestic animals:** ot (лошадь - horse), aygir (жеребец - stallion), biya (кобылица - mare), qou (овца - sheep), qochqor (баран - ram), sovliq (овца - ewe), buqa (бык - bull), xo'kiz (вол - ox), sigir (корова - cow), tana (телка - heifer), xo'roz (петух - rooster), tovuq (курица - hen).

2.

Syntactic**Means.**

Gender can also be expressed syntactically, by adding gender markers to a noun: o'qituvchi erkak („женщина-врач“, „женщина-судья“, „мужчина-прачка“ male teacher), o'qituvchi ayol („женщина-врач“, „женщина-судья“, „мужчина-прачка“ female teacher), bo'ri erkak („мужчина-прачка“ male wolf), urg'ochi bo'ri (female wolf).

Syntactic method of expressing gender

Gender marker	Example (Uzbek/Russian)	English meaning
er (man)	er bola (мальчик)	boy (lit. “male child”)
qiz (girl)	qiz bola (девочка)	girl (lit. “female child”)
(no marker)	bola (ребёнок)	child (common gender)
erkak (man)	o'roqchi (erkak) (жнец)	male reaper
xotin/ayol (woman)	o'roqchi (ayol/xotin) (жница)	female reaper

Gender marker	Example (Uzbek/Russian)	English meaning
erkak (man)	ishchi (erkak) (рабочий)	male worker
xotin/ayol (woman)	ishchi (ayol/xotin) (работница)	female worker
erkak (man)	o‘qituvchi (erkak) (учитель)	male teacher
xotin/ayol (woman)	o‘qituvchi (ayol/xotin) (учительница)	female teacher
erkak (male)	ayiq (erkak) (медведь)	male bear
urg‘ochi (female)	urg‘ochi ayiq (медведица)	female bear
erkak (male)	arslon/sher (erkak) (лев)	lion (male)
urg‘ochi (female)	urg‘ochi arslon/sher (львица)	lioness
erkak (male)	bo‘ri (erkak) (волк)	male wolf
urg‘ochi (female)	urg‘ochi bo‘ri (волчица)	she-wolf

3. Morphological Means.

Though limited in productivity, gender can be shown through specific affixes, often used historically to denote women of noble rank or to form feminine counterparts:

Among the suffixes that form the **feminine gender** of nouns are:

1. **-im**:

- xonim (ханша, госпожа) ← xon (“khan”)
- bekim (жена бека, госпожа) ← bek (бек)

According to Ramstedt, the suffix **-im** presumably goes back to the Mongolian word eme = “woman.” Other scholars compare this suffix with the 1st person singular possessive suffix. There is also a hypothesis that **-m / -mik** is a **diminutive suffix**; this assumption deserves the greatest attention, given that all

other suffixes forming names of the female gender are diminutive in meaning. Cf. the meaning of the element -м in the structure of the suffix -мси < м + си < -сиг.

2. **General-gender noun**, combining both females and males; cf. Uzbek ot and Russian „лошадь“ (“horse”).

3. **Xotin** (женщина замужняя; married woman); **ayol** — a general designation for the female gender, including both girls and women.

4. **-chi** (-chik — diminutive suffix): egachi (старшая сестра) ← og‘a (“aka,” elder brother).

5. **-(a)ch** (diminutive suffix): bekach || bikach (бекач; “daughter of a bek, lady”), a respectful form of address to a woman.

6. **-chin | -jin | -jik:**

- borchin (утка-самка, female duck)
- g‘unajin (телка по третьему году, a heifer in its third year).

4. **Phonetic** **Means.**

In rare cases, gender is marked by internal vowel alternation: buva (grandfather) – buvi (grandmother).

Gender Category in Russian

In Russian, gender is one of the core grammatical categories of the noun. Words ending in a consonant are generally masculine (стол, герой, отец), those ending in -а/-я are feminine (мама, неделя, лошадь), and those ending in -о/-е are neuter (окно, море, слово).

There are exceptions: папа, дядя, дедушка — masculine by meaning despite feminine endings; кофе — masculine by tradition; пальто, такси, жури — neuter.

As Yu. N. Karaulov (1987) notes, the interconnection between lexicon and grammar is inseparable: “For the speaker, grammar and vocabulary exist as a unified system of linguistic knowledge that functions dynamically in speech.”

Other Grammatical Categories

Russian nouns possess the categories of **gender**, **number**, **case**, and **animacy/inanimacy**, whereas Uzbek nouns have **number**, **case**, **possession**, **definiteness–indefiniteness**, and **person–nonperson** categories. The most contrasting categories are **gender** (present in Russian, absent in Uzbek) and **person–nonperson** (present in Uzbek, absent in Russian), which significantly affect word-formation and conceptual distinctions between the two linguistic systems.

In Russian, nouns denoting people and animals are **animate** (answering кто? — учитель, врач, собака), while all others are **inanimate** (answering что? — город, карандаш, независимость).

As researchers note, such grammatical and semantic contrasts reflect deeper differences between the linguistic worldviews of the Russian and Uzbek peoples (Rahmatullaev, 1993; Tomchani, 2017).

References

1. Azizov O. Safaev A. Jamolxonov. O‘zbek va rus tillarining qiyosiy grammatikasi. T., 1986.
2. Киссен И.А. Курс сопоставительной грамматики русского и узбекского языков. Т., 1979.
3. Mahmudov N., Nurmonov A. O‘zbek tilining nazariy grammatikasi. T., 1965.
4. Rahmatullaev Sh. O‘zbek va rus tillarini qiyoslash. T., 1993; 19-22-betlar.
5. Reshetov V.V., Reshetova L.V. Rus tili grammatikasi. Toshkent: «O‘qituvchi», 1968.
6. Современный русский язык. Под ред. Белошапковой. М.: «Высшая школа», 1989.
7. Томчани, Л. В. Типологические контрасты русского и узбекского языков в методическом аспекте / Л. В. Томчани. — Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. — 2017. — № 14 (148). — С. 736-738.